

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/305660637>

Exploring Possibilities of Implementation of Special Rutile Electrodes for Welding Microalloyed Steels

Article in *Advanced Materials Research* · July 2016

DOI: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.1138.19

CITATIONS

0

READS

179

6 authors, including:

Nikola Bajic

IHS Science And Technology Park

34 PUBLICATIONS 134 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Marko Rakin

University of Belgrade

230 PUBLICATIONS 3,247 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Darko M. Veljic

Inovation Center of the Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade

48 PUBLICATIONS 214 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Zoran Radosavljevic

24 PUBLICATIONS 139 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

TR 19061 [View project](#)

ON 174004, TR34016 [View project](#)

Exploring possibilities of implementation of special rutile electrodes for welding microalloyed steels

Mihailo Mrdak^{1,a}, Nikola Bajić^{2,b*}, Marko Rakin^{3,c}, Darko Veljić^{2,b}, Zoran Karastojković^{4,d}, Zoran Radosavljević^{5b}

¹Research and Development Center, IMTEL Communications a.d., Mihajla Pupina 165b, 11070 Belgrade, Serbia

² IHIS Techno-experts d.o.o. - Research and Development Center, Batajnički drum 23, 11080 Belgrade, Serbia

³ Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Karnegijeva 4, 11120 Belgrade, Serbia

⁴Advanced Technical School for Vocational Studies, 11070 Belgrade, Serbia

⁵Research and Development institute Lola Ltd., Kneza Visislava 70a, 11030 Belgrade, Serbia

^adrmrdakmihailo@gmail.com, ^cmarko@tmf.bg.ac.rs ^dzoran.karastojkovic@gmail.com

^{b*} [Corresponding author: ihis@EUnet.rs](mailto:ihis@EUnet.rs),

Keywords: special electrode, microalloyed steel, weld metal, chemical composition, mechanical properties, microstructure

Abstract. The paper presents test results of a new quality of a special rutile electrode, with a core of flux-cored wire made from local raw materials, based on analyzing mechanical properties and microstructure of the weld metal in MMA welding. The base metal for experimental welding was microalloyed steel marked J55 (thickness 7.0 mm) according to API Spec 5L standards (EN 10113-3. and JUS C.B0 502) which was produced in Smederevo steelworks. For experimental welding a special electrode IHIS E 35 R-2 was used, with a medium thickness rutile coating, a core of flux-cored wire and Ni content of 2.5%. The results of the analyzes indicate that the new quality special rutile electrode with the flux-cored wire core provides good structural and mechanical properties of weld metal in microalloyed steel welded joints.

Introduction

Development of microalloyed steel is followed by development of electrodes for efficient joining by welding, which should correspond to the properties of the base metal. The main condition that must be met by each welded construction is safety in use. In order to meet this demand, properties of the welded joints are crucial.

In the welded joint of great importance are properties of weld metal and HAZ. The basic rule is that the weld metal should have better properties than the base metal which is achieved by appropriate alloying of the weld metal with filler. In order to create the most favorable microstructure in the weld metal with optimum mechanical properties, special rutile electrodes were developed and manufactured with a core of flux-cored wires with a thicker wall of the metal casing.

Production of rutile coated electrodes with a core of alloyed flux-cored wire involves the development of a special electrode coating formula. The main role of the coating is to stabilize the arc, deoxidize, additionally alloy the welded joint and form slag on the surface of the liquid weld metal to protect against external influences. The preferred structure of the weld metal with the rutile coating and a core of flux-cored wire system requires a precisely defined composition of coating components and composition of the alloyed core of the flux-cored wire because there is a narrow range of oxygen content in the weld metal, which provides formation of a large share of acicular ferrite in the structure.

Electrode coatings are a multicomponent system which in welding conditions, are far from equilibrium, and due to the complexity and interactions of a significant number of influential factors it is difficult to precisely define their influence on the composition of the weld metal. The chemical composition of rutile coatings and alloyed flux-cored wires is designed with the primary goal for the weld metal to have a large percentage of needle-like ferrite, then to increase the strength and toughness of the weld metal by adding micro alloying elements and to, by purification, reduce the content of S, P, H, O and N in the weld metal and thus provide the possibility of application for welding microalloyed steels [1-3].

During welding, it is necessary to optimize the welding mode that will best create the optimal microstructure of the weld metal with optimal mechanical properties [4]. Chemical composition and cooling rate are the two main factors that directly determine the microstructure of the weld metal. Chemical composition of weld metal is determined by the type of fillers used and partially influenced by the base metal which melts during welding, while the cooling rate is largely dictated by welding parameters, or heat input during welding.

Mechanical properties and impact toughness of a welded joint greatly depend on the microstructure of the weld metal. Acicular ferrite is the most desirable form of microstructure in weld metal of low-carbon low-alloyed steel, due to its positive effect on the mechanical properties [5]. Formation of the microstructure of acicular ferrite is a complex phenomenon and depends on many factors. Some of them are: the type, size and number of inclusions, type of shielding atmosphere during welding, cooling rate, type of filler, welding heat input and other. [6]. Fine and evenly distributed particles of inclusions in the weld metal support the formation of needlelike-acicular ferrite [7-9].

The aim of development and experimental work was to master the technological process of producing a special rutile coated electrode with a flux-cored wire core based on domestic raw materials. This paper analyzes the impact of the composition of the special coated rutile electrode with a flux-cored wire core on mechanical properties and the share of acicular ferrite in the weld metal, which increases the safety of welded structures in working conditions. For experimental welding the base metal selected was microalloyed steel marked J55 according to API Spec 5L thickness of 7.0 mm, produced in Smederevo Steelworks.

Materials and experimental details

For the experimental work selected as the base metal was hot-rolled thermo-mechanically processed steel strip thickness of 7.0 mm of microalloyed steel marked J55 according to API Spec 5L, standards EN 10113-3 and JUS C.B0 502. Marking and chemical composition of microalloyed steel J55 are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Chemical composition of steel J55

Steel	Chemical composition, wt.%						
	C	Si	Mn	Al	Cu	Ti	Nb
J55	0.06	0.27	1.31	0.026	0.02	0.011	0.027

Table 2 shows values of the mechanical properties of steel J55 and defined values as per standard API 5CT [10].

Table 2 Tensile strength of the base metal J55

Base metal	R_e , [MPa]	R_m , [MPa]	A_5 , [%]
J55	491	569	25
Standard API 5CT	379 - 552	> 517	> 22.5

For welding experimental samples a special rutile electrode IHIS E 35 R-2 was selected with a core of flux-cored wire 350 mm in length and Ø3.25 mm in diameter with a medium coating thickness

designed for MMA welding and surfacing. Table 3 shows the welding parameters for steel J55 using the MMA welding procedure.

Table 3 Welding parameters for steel J55 samples for MMA welding procedure

Special electrode marking	d [mm]	Welding parameters			Number of passes	Linear energy [KJ/cm]
		U [V]	I [A]	V [cm/min]		
IHIS E 35 R-2	3.25	24	125	23-30	5+k	7.5-8.5

The chemical composition of the base metal and pure weld metal were tested using spectrochemical analysis - OES method on the ARL 2460 device. Tests of tensile properties of weld metal of welded joints were done on the AMSLER wear machine according to standards EN 895 and SRPS EN 10002-1/1 on specimens made according to JUS C.T3054.

For toughness testing, standard Charpy V notch specimens were used with the tip of the notch in the primary microstructure of the weld metal. Resistance of weld metal to brittle fracture was conducted by impact examining at a temperature of -40°C with determining of consumed energy of impact KV (J). Impact toughness testing was performed according to standard JUS C.T3051.

Examination of the microstructure of the base metal and quantitative analysis of acicular ferrite (AF) in the weld metal in the last passing was performed under a "Leitz" light microscope. Applied was the linear method of measuring cut offs at a magnification of x500. Qualitative analysis of the weld metal of welded joints was done in etched condition on the scanning electron microscope (SEM). Etching of the weld metal was done in a 3% solution of nital.

Test results

The chemical composition of pure weld metal of welded samples made using a special rutile electrode marked IHIS E 35 R-2 with a core of flux-cored wire is shown in Table 4. Testing the chemical composition was conducted to determine the effect of nickel from the core of the flux-cored wire of the rutile electrodes on the mechanical properties and microstructure of the weld metal of the welded joint. Table 5 shows the value of mechanical properties of pure weld metal of welded joints. Mechanical properties of pure weld metal of welded joints such as yield stress Re [MPa], tensile strength Rm [MPa], elongation A₅ [%] and impact energy KV (J) are in direct relation to the content of Ni and Mo in the weld metal. The nickel from rutile electrode with a flux-cored wire core had favorable influence on the mechanical properties of the weld metal, which indicates that in the microstructure of the weld metal a greater share of acicular ferrite is present.

Table 4 Chemical composition of pure weld metal

Chemical composition, wt.%							
C	Si	Mn	Cu	Cr	Mo	Ni	Ti
0.08	0.53	1.23	0.064	0.043	0.36	2.48	0.02

Molybdenum, which is considered very important for achieving an optimal ratio of structural components and added to the coated flux cored-wire increased hardenability of the weld metal, made the primary microstructure finer, increased the amount of acicular ferrite, removed the upper bainite retaining only the thin platelets of primary proeutectoid ferrite and polygonal ferrite in the base of the weld metal. This was confirmed by metallographic tests of the weld metal on the scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Table 5 Marking of the special electrode and mechanical properties of weld metal

Electrode marking	d [mm]	Mechanical properties of weld metal			
		Re [MPa]	Rm [MPa]	A ₅ [%]	KV(J) [-40 °C]
IHIS E 35 R-2	3.25	495	570	24.5	54

The breaking of the weld metal (WM) at -40°C showed a tough property, which indicates that Ni and Mo had favorable impact on the resistance of the weld metal to brittle fracture. Ni and Mo in the

weld metal, at the expense of acicular ferrite, lowered the share of primary proeutectoid and polygonal ferrite, which had a favorable effect on toughness. Mechanical properties of the weld metal show that the tested weld metal is safe at -40°C .

Figure 1a shows the micrographs of the microstructure of the base metal (BM), a steel strip thickness of 7.0 mm of micro alloyed steel marked J55. The microstructure of steel J55 is homogeneous ferrite - pearlite with strip-directional metal grains in the rolling direction.

Fig. 1 The microstructure: a) (BM) of the base metal J55; b) (SEM) of the weld metal

Figure 1b shows scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of the microstructure of pure weld metal alloyed with 2.48% Ni and 0.36% Mo.

The microstructure of the weld metal consists of austenite grains with formed boundary proeutectoid and intergranular polygonal ferrite (PF) which are formed along the austenite grain boundaries during cooling of the austenite.

Ferrite formed along grain boundaries in the form of intergranular discontinuous layers is boundary polygonal ferrite (PF). It can also be formed within the austenite grains with constant thickness as hypo-eutectoid or intragranular ferrite. The share of proeutectoid and polygonal ferrite (PF) is reduced at the expense of needle - acicular ferrite (AF) at a faster rate of solidification and cooling of weld metal and with a larger content of Ni and Mo in the weld metal. In the austenite grains of the weld metal (WM) acicular ferrite (AF) is dominant.

Volume share of acicular ferrite in the weld metal (WM) of the welded joint was 78.35% (AF), while 21.65% were morphological forms, proeutectoid and polygonal ferrite (PF). The SEM micrographs clearly show the randomly oriented ferrite needle crystals formed as a woven mesh which increases the resistance of the weld metal to brittle fracture. In the austenitic grains along the acicular ferrite (AF) boundaries present are spherical nonmetallic inclusions from the rutile coating, which served as nuclei of intragranular nucleation of needle like ferrite [11-13].

In the microstructure of the weld metal there was no Widmanstatten ferrite or ferrite with secondary phases observed. The microstructure of the weld metal of the welded joint is in full compliance with the mechanical properties. The results of testing the mechanical properties and microstructure of the weld metal of welded joints confirmed that the special rutile electrodes marked IHIS E 35 R-2 were of reliable quality and can be successfully applied for welding microalloyed steels.

Conclusion

This paper analyzes the characterization of the weld metal (WM) of welded joints of microalloyed steel J55 Smederevo Steelworks made using a special rutile electrode with a flux-cored wire core based on domestic raw materials. Based on the results obtained by experimental examination of the impact of

the quality of the new filler on properties of weld metal of the welded joint the following conclusions were made:

The results of testing the mechanical properties of the weld metal (WM) of the welded joint made with the new special rutile electrode with a flux-cored wire core; show that the mastered quality of the rutile electrode has a high technological level, due to well-designed chemical composition of the rutile coating and the flux-cored wire.

By using special electrode IHIS E 35 R-2 for welding steel J55 with MMA welding procedure very good values were achieved of yield stress, tensile strength and toughness of the weld metal of the welded joint with heat input of 7.5-8.5 KJ / cm.

In the weld metal microstructure there is a high share of acicular ferrite which is evenly distributed in the austenite grains, indicating a homogeneous distribution of Ni and Mo in the rutile electrode with a flux-cored wire core based on domestic raw materials.

The obtained results confirmed that the special coated rutile electrode with a flux-cored wire core and the use of a significant proportion of domestic raw materials can be successfully applied for welding microalloyed steels.

Acknowledgements

This paper is supported by the Serbian Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development. Projects: TR34016 "Development of covering and core production technology based on local raw materials for manufacturing of special coated electrodes designed for steel arc welding" & TR 35002 "Development of new methodologies for revitalizing turbine and hydro mechanical equipment of hydroelectric power stations depending on the cause of degradation of the material".

References

- [1] M. Mrdak, N. Bajić, M. Rakin, S. Stojadinović, D. Veljić, Comparison of the microstructure of weld metals in welded joints made with rutile electrodes based on domestic raw materials and electrodes of a well-known manufacturer, ANNALS of Faculty Engineering Hunedoara International Journal of Engineering, Tome XIII, 2015, pp.75-78.
- [2] M. Mrdak, N. Bajić, M. Rakin, S. Stojadinović, J. Pekez, Comparison of the microstructure of weld metals in welded joints made with rutile electrodes based on domestic raw materials and electrodes of a well-known manufacturer, IV International Conference Industrial Engineering and Environmental Protection (IIZS 2014), 2014, pp.119-122.
- [3] M. Mrdak, N. Bajić, M. Rakin, D. Veljić, V. Grabulov, Analysis of the structure of the weld metal made with a basic type coated electrode, The 3rd IIW South-East European Welding Congress June 03-05, Timisoara, Romania, Welding and joining technologies for a sustainable development and environment, 2015, pp.1-4.
- [4] M. Rakin, N. Bajić, M. Mrdak, D. Veljić, M. Arsić, Analysis of mechanical and structural properties of micro alloyed steel welded joints depending on quality of cored wire, Tehnički vjesnik 20, 4, 2013, pp.635-640.
- [5] P.T. Oldland, C.W. Ramsy, D.K. Matlock, D.L. Olson, Significant Features of High-Strength Steel Weld Metal Microstructure, Welding Journal, 1989, p.158.
- [6] R. Prokić-Cvetković, A. Milosavljević, A. Sedmak, Z. Burzić, Uticaj unete količine toplote pri zavarivanju na žilavost metala šava mikrolegiranih čelika. Zavarivanje i zavarene konstrukcije, 45, 3, 2000, pp.107-112.

- [7] S. Liu, J.E. Indacochea, Control of Chemical Composition and Microstructure in Low - Carbon Microalloyed Steel Weldments, IIW Doc II-A-886-93.
- [8] G.M. Evans, The Effect of Heat input on the Microstructure and Properties of all Weld Metal Deposits, *Welding Journal*, 61, 4, 1982, pp.125-132.
- [9] G.M. Evans, The Effect of Interpass Temperature on the Microstructure and Properties of all Weld Metal Deposits, *Welding Review*, 1, 1982, pp.14-20.
- [10] API Spec 5CT, Specification for casing and tubing, American Petroleum Institute, 2002.
- [11] G.L.F. Powell, G. Herfurth, CharpyV-notch properties and microstructures of narrow gap ferritic welds of a quenched and tempered steel plate. *Metall. Mater. Trans. A: Phys. Metall. Mater. Sci.*, 29A,11, 1998, pp.2775 – 2784.
- [12] T. Wegrzyn, Classification of metal weld deposits in terms of the amount of nitrogen. In: *Proceedings of the 10th International Offshore and Polar Engineering Conference*, 4, 11, 2000, pp.130 – 134.
- [13] J.F. dos Santos, V.R. dos Santos, J.C. Jorge, Properties of a ferritic metal cored wire weld metal deposited in the pressure range from 51 bar to 110 bar. *Proceedings of the 6th International Offshore and Polar Engineering Conference*, Part 4, Los Angeles, CA, USA, 1996, pp.141–146.